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Silk granuloma at gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma.

Abdul Redah AL-Rawaf
Consultant surgeon,
Department of surgery
University Hospital in Al Kadhymiyia

Abstract

Silk granuloma has been reported as benign complication seen after surgery. Suture granuloma can occur many months or years after the primary surgical procedure. The most common suture causing tissue irritation and subsequent granuloma is probably the silk (non-absorbable suture) especially braided one. The diagnosis in cases of granuloma occurring at gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma is generally made at endoscopic examination. The aim of this paper is to report the cases of stitch granuloma observed at upper gastrointestinal endoscopy.

From January 1987 to October 1987 100 patients were referred for upper gastrointestinal endoscopy for various reasons. Silk granuloma at gastric side of gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma for duodenal ulcer operation were found in 7 patients (7%). All of the patients were treated by removal of silk by endoscopic forceps.

Keywords: Stitch-Silk granuloma-postoperative-anastomosis-endoscopy.

Introduction

Silk granuloma has been reported as benign complication seen after surgery. Suture granuloma can occur many months or years after the primary surgical procedure. The

most common suture causing tissue irritation and subsequent granuloma is probably the silk (non-absorbable suture) especially braided one. The granuloma presents as a chronic intermittent indolent infection commonly known as stitch abscess. The diagnosis in cases of granuloma occurring at gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma is generally made at endoscopic examination . Monofilament and recently manufactured absorbable suture has been associated with a lower risk of infection. Curative treatment is removal of the infected suture material (silk) by endoscopic biopsy forceps [1,2,3,4].

Patient and Methods

From January 1987 to October 1987 100 patients were referred to us at the University Hospital in Al Kadhymiyia for upper gastrointestinal endoscopy for various reasons.

Results

Silk granuloma at gastric side of gastrointestinal anastomosis stoma for duodenal ulcer operation were found in 7 patients (7%), they were located at gastric side of the stoma with evidence of ulceration and easy bleeding glaucomatous area. All of the patients were treated by removal of silk by endoscopic forceps

Discussion

Most of the surgeons in Iraq are treat duodenal ulcer when necessary by vagotomy and drainage operation (pyloplasty or gastro-jejunosomy). In both these types two layers anastomosis are applied, the inner absorbable and outré non- absorbable (silk) sutures, both of continuous layers. The outer silk layer form non-elastic ring like band around the anastomosed stoma. By time and with action of peristaltic movement, this band pushed from the outer sero-muscular layer toward inner sub-epithelial layer, with it's irritating effect and tissue reaction forming granuloma. Therefore intra abdominal contamination with foreign material should be minimized. Silk granuloma can occur in the bronchial stump after lung resection, in the lung parenchyma after segmentectomy or as a paravesical mass or abscess after inguinal hernia repair .The use of synthetic absorbable sutures especially those with delayed absorbable monofilament sutures such as polydioxanon (PDS), Maxon (polyglyconate), ,polycolic sutures(Dexon), polyglatid sutures(vicryl), poliglecapron monofilament(Monocryl) ,and poliglecapron braided sutures (panacryl) could possibly lower the incidence of stitch granuloma as they elicit lower tissue reaction and lower affinity for bacteria as well as fair knot security than natural absorption [1,2,3,4].

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